
Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Floating Microspheres of Nizatidine for Gastroretentive Drug Delivery

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Abstract: Floating microspheres loaded with Nizatidine were prepared using solvent- evaporation method using HPMC, Eudragit RL 100, Eudragit RLPO in different ratio polymers. Drug and polymer in proportion of drug and polymers were dissolved in 1:2 mixture of solvent system of ethanol and dichloromethane. Floating microspheres of Nizatidine were prepared by a solvent diffusion- evaporation method. The nature of polymer influenced the physical characteristics as well as floating behaviour of the microspheres. In vitro buoyancy and in vivo studies confirmed the excellent floating properties of HPMC, Eudragit RL 100, Eudragit RLPO microspheres. The drug release was sufficiently sustained and non-Fickian transport of the drug from floating microspheres was confirmed. Hence the floating microspheres of Nizatidine, may provide a convenient dosage form for achieving best performance regarding flow, release and floating properties. Further, their potential to improve Nizatidine bioavailability in humans needs to be investigated in further studies.

Keywords: Floating microspheres, Nizatidine, Solvent evaporation method, Bioavailability

Introduction

Gastroretentive Dosage Form (GRDF):

It is evident from the recent scientific and patient literature that an increased interest in novel dosage forms that are retained in stomach for a prolonged and predictable period of time exists today in academic and industrial research groups. One of the most feasible approaches for achieving a prolonged and predictable drug delivery in the GI tract is to control the gastric residence time (GRT), i.e. gastro retentive dosage form (GRDF or GRDS).

GRDFs extend significantly the period of time over which the drugs may be released. They not only prolong dosing intervals, but also increase patient compliance beyond the level of existing controlled release dosage form.

Dosage form with prolonged GRT, i.e. gastro retentive dosage form (GRDF), will bring about new and important therapeutic options such as

- 1) This application is especially effective in sparingly soluble and insoluble drugs. It is known that, as the solubility of a drug decreases, the time available for drug dissolution becomes less adequate and thus the transit time becomes a significant factor affecting drug absorption. To override this problem, erodible, gastroretentive dosage forms have been developed that provide continuous, controlled administration of sparingly soluble drugs at the absorption site.
- 2) GRDFs greatly improve the pharmacotherapy of the stomach through local drug release, leading to high drug concentration at the gastric mucosa. (For e.g. Eradicating *Helicobacter pylori* from the submucosal tissue of

stomach) making it possible to treat stomach and duodenal ulcers, gastritis and oesophagitis, reduce the risk of gastric carcinoma and administer non-systemic controlled release antacid formulations (calcium carbonate).

3) GRDFs can be used as carriers for drugs with so-called absorption windows. These substances for e.g. antiviral, antifungal and antibiotic agents (sulphonamides, quinolones,

4) Penicillins, cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, tetracyclines etc.), are taken up only from very specific sites of the GI mucosa.

Biological Aspects of GRDFs:

Role of GI tract: Stomach

The stomach is J-shaped organ located in the upper left hand portion of the abdomen, just below the diaphragm. It occupies a portion of the epigastric and left hydrochondriac region. The main function of the stomach is to store the food temporarily, grind it and then release it slowly into the duodenum. Due to its small surface area very little absorption takes place from the stomach. It provides barrier to the delivery of drugs to small intestine.

Figure 1: Anatomy of Stomach

The stomach is divided into three anatomical regions. I) Fundus ii) Body and iii) Pylorus (or antrum). The proximal stomach consisted of fundus and body, which serves as a reservoir for ingested materials, whereas the distal region (pylorus) is the major site of mixing motions, acting as a pump to propel gastric contents for gastric emptying. Gastric emptying occurs both in fasting as well as fed states.

The GI tract is always in a state of continuous motility. There are two modes of motility pattern. The digestive mode and inter-digestive mode. In case of fasted state an inter digestive series of electrical events occurs in cyclic manner both through stomach and small intestine every 2-3 hr.

Approaches to Gastric Retention

1. Floating System
2. Bio/Muco-adhesive Systems
3. Swelling and Expanding Systems
4. High Density System
5. Incorporation of Passage Delaying Food Agents
6. Ion Exchange Resins
7. Osmotic Regulated Systems

Types of Floating Drug Delivery Systems (FDDS)

Based on the mechanism of buoyancy, two distinctly different technologies have been utilized in development of FDDS which are:

- A. Effervescent System, and
 B. Non- Effervescent System.

A. Effervescent System:-

Effervescent systems include use of gas generating agents, carbonates (ex. Sodium bicarbonate) and other organic acid (e.g. citric acid and tartaric acid) present in the formulation to produce carbon dioxide (CO₂) gas, thus reducing the density of the system and making it float on the gastric fluid. An alternative is the incorporation of matrix containing portion of liquid, which produce gas that evaporate at body temperature.

These effervescent systems further classified into two types.

I. Gas Generating systems

II. Volatile Liquid/Vacuum Containing Systems.

I. Gas – Generating Systems:

1. Intra Gastric Single Layer Floating Tablets or Hydrodynamically Balanced System (HBS):

These are as shown in Figure 4 and formulated by intimately mixing the CO₂ generating agents and the drug with in the matrix tablet. These have a bulk density lower than gastric fluids and therefore remain floating in the stomach unflattering the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period. The drug is slowly released at a desired rate from the floating system and after the complete release the residual system is expelled from the stomach. This leads to an increase in the GRT and a better control over fluctuations in plasma drug concentration.

Figure 2: Intra Gastric Single Layer Floating Tablet.

2. Intra Gastric Bilayer Floating Tablets:

These are also compressed tablet as shown in Fig 6 and containing two layer i.e.,

- i. Immediate release layer and
- ii. Sustained release layer.

Figure 3: Intra Gastric Bilayer Floating Tablet.

3. Multiple Unit type floating pills:

These system consist of sustained release pills as 'seeds' surrounded by double layers. The inner layer consist of effervescent agents while the outer layer is of swellable membrane layer. When the system is immersed in dissolution medium at body temp, it sinks at once and then forms swollen pills like balloons, which float as they have lower density. This lower density is due to generation and entrapment of CO₂ within the system.

Figure 4: (a) A multi-unit oral floating dosage system. (b) Stages of floating mechanism: (A) penetration of water; (B) generation of CO₂ and floating; (C) dissolution of drug. Key: (a) conventional SR pills; (b) effervescent layer; (c) swellable layer; (d) expanded swellable membrane layer; (e) surface of water in the beaker (37°C).

II. Volatile Liquid / Vacuum Containing Systems:

1. Intra-gastric Floating Gastrointestinal Drug Delivery System:

These system can be made to float in the stomach because of floatation chamber, which may be a vacuum or filled with air or a harmless gas, while drug reservoir is encapsulated inside a microporous compartment, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Intra Gastric Floating Gastrointestinal Drug Delivery Device

2. Inflatable Gastrointestinal Delivery Systems:

In these systems an inflatable chamber is incorporated, which contains liquid ether that gasifies at body temperature to cause the chamber to inflate in the stomach. These systems are fabricated by loading the inflatable chamber with a drug reservoir, which can be a drug impregnated polymeric matrix, then encapsulated in a gelatin capsule. After oral administration, the capsule dissolves to release the drug reservoir together with the inflatable chamber. The inflatable chamber automatically inflates and retains the drug reservoir compartment in the stomach. The drug continuously released from the reservoir into the gastric fluid. This system is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Inflatable Gastrointestinal Delivery System

3. Intra-gastric Osmotically Controlled Drug Delivery System:

It is comprised of an osmotic pressure controlled drug delivery device and an inflatable floating support in a biodegradable capsule. In the stomach, the capsule quickly disintegrates to release the intra-gastric osmotically controlled drug delivery device. The inflatable support inside forms a deformable hollow polymeric bag that contains a liquid that gasifies at body temperature to inflate the bag. The osmotic pressure controlled drug delivery device consist of two components; drug reservoir compartment and an osmotically active compartment.

The drug reservoir compartment is enclosed by a pressure responsive collapsible bag, which is impermeable to vapour and liquid and has a drug delivery orifice. The osmotically active compartment contains an osmotically active salt and is enclosed within a semipermeable housing. In the stomach, the water in the GI fluid is continuously absorbed through the semipermeable membrane into osmotically active compartment to dissolve the osmotically active salt. An osmotic pressure is thus created which acts on the collapsible bag and in turn forces the drug reservoir compartment to reduce its volume and activate the drug reservoir compartment to reduce its volume and activate the drug release of a drug solution formulation through the delivery orifice.

The floating support is also made to contain a bioerodible plug that erodes after a predetermined time to deflate the support. The deflated drug delivery system is then emptied from the stomach. This system is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Intra-gastric Osmotically Controlled Drug Delivery System

B. Non-Effervescent Systems:

The Non-effervescent FDDS based on mechanism of swelling of polymer or bioadhesion to mucosal layer in GI tract. The most commonly used excipients in non-effervescent FDDS are gel forming or highly swellable cellulose type hydrocolloids, polysaccharides and matrix forming material such as polycarbonate, polyacrylate, polymethacrylate, polystyrene as well as bioadhesive polymer such as chitosan and carbopol. The various types of this system are as:

1. Single Layer Floating Tablets:

They are formulated by intimate mixing of drug with a gel-forming hydrocolloid, which swells in contact with gastric fluid and maintain bulk density of less than unity. The air trapped by the swollen polymer confers buoyancy to these dosage forms.

2. Bilayer Floating Tablets:

A bilayer tablet contain two layer one immediate release layer which release initial dose from system while the another sustained release layer absorbs gastric fluid, forming an impermeable colloidal gel barrier on its surface, and maintain a bulk density of less than unity and thereby it remains buoyant in the stomach.

3. Alginate Beads:

Multiunit floating dosage forms were developed from freeze-dried calcium alginate. Spherical beads of approximately 2.5 mm diameter can be prepared by dropping a sodium alginate solution into aqueous solution of calcium chloride, causing precipitation of calcium alginate leading to formation of porous system, which can maintain a floating force for over 12 hours. When compared with solid beads, which gave a short residence time of 1 hour, these floating beads gave a prolonged residence time of more than 5.5 hour.

4. Hollow Microspheres:

Hollow microspheres (microballoons), loaded with drug in their outer polymer shells were prepared by a novel emulsion-solvent diffusion method. The ethanol:dichloromethane solution of the drug and an enteric acrylic polymer was poured into an agitated aqueous solution of PVA that was thermally controlled at 40°C. The gas phase generated in dispersed polymer droplet by evaporation of dichloromethane formed an internal cavity in microsphere of polymer with drug. The microballoons floated continuously over the surface of acidic dissolution media containing surfactant for more than 12 hours in vitro.

Microspheres

Microspheres are defined as “Monolithic sphere or therapeutic agent distributed throughout the matrix either as a molecular dispersion of particles” (or) can be defined as structure made up of continuous phase of one or more miscible polymers in which drug particles are dispersed at the molecular or macroscopic level. Microspheres are small spherical particles, with diameters in the micrometer range (typically 1 µm to 1000 µm).

Microspheres are sometimes referred to as microparticles. Biodegradable synthetic polymers and modified natural products such as starches, gums, proteins, fats and waxes. The natural polymers include albumin and gelatin, the synthetic polymer include poly lactic acid and polyglycolic acid.

The solvents used to dissolve the polymeric materials chosen according to the polymer and drug solubility and stabilities, process safety and economic considerations¹⁹. Microspheres for oral use have been employed to sustain the drug release, and to reduce or eliminate gastrointestinal tract irritation. In addition, multiparticulate delivery systems spread out more uniformly in the gastrointestinal tract.

Nizatidine competes with histamine for binding at the H₂- receptors on the gastric basolateral membrane of parietal cells. Competitive inhibition results in reduction of basal and nocturnal gastric acid secretions. The drug also decreases the gastric acid response to stimuli such as food, caffeine, insulin, betazole, or pentagastrin.

Protein binding: 35%

Metabolism: Hepatic. Less than 7% of an oral dose is metabolized as N₂-monodes- methyl nizatidine, an H₂-receptor antagonist, which is the principal metabolite excreted in the urine. Other likely metabolites are the N₂-oxide (less than 5% of the dose) and the S-oxide (less than 6% of the dose).

Half-life: 1-2 hours

Uses

Nizatidine is used to treat and prevent the recurrence of ulcers and to treat other conditions where the stomach makes too much acid. Nizatidine also is used to treat or prevent occasional heartburn, acid indigestion, or sour stomach. It decreases the amount of acid made in the stomach.

2. Preparation And Characterization

Preparation of floating microsphere of Nizatidine

Floating microspheres loaded with Nizatidine were prepared using solvent- evaporation method using HPMC, Eudragit RL 100, Eudragit RSPO in different ratio table 1. Drug and polymer in proportion of drug and polymers were dissolved in 1:2 mixture of solvent system of ethanol and dichloromethane. This clear solution was poured slowly in a thin stream into the aqueous solution of 1% polyvinyl alcohol. The emulsion was continuously stirred for 3 h at a speed of 500 rpm at 27±2°C. The floating microspheres were collected by decantation, while the non-floating microspheres were discarded. The microspheres were dried overnight at 40±2°C and stored in desiccator.

Table 1: Formulations of the floating microspheres prepared

S. No.	Formulation Code	Nizatidine (mg)	HPMC (mg)	Eudragit RL100 (mg)	Eudragit RSPO (mg)
1.	F1	75	100	25	-
2.	F2	75	100	50	-
3.	F3	75	100	75	-
4.	F4	75	150	25	10
5.	F5	75	150	50	20

3. Evaluation of Nizatidine Floating Microspheres

Percentage Yield

Percentage yield of different formulation was determined by weighing the Microspheres after drying. The percentage yield of different formulation was in range of 65.58 ± 0.25 – $78.85 \pm 0.36\%$. The maximum percentage yield was found in formulation F5, 78.85 ± 0.36 as compare to all formulation.

Table 2: Percentage yield for different formulation

S. No.	Formulation	Percentage Yield
1.	F1	65.58 ± 0.25
2.	F2	69.95 ± 0.36
3.	F3	67.74 ± 0.21
4.	F4	73.32 ± 0.40
5.	F5	78.85 ± 0.36
6.	F6	70.14 ± 0.32

Figure 8: Percentage yield for different formulation

Drug Entrapment

The drug entrapment of all formulations was determined spectrophotometrically. The drug entrapment efficacies of different formulations were in range of 65.56 ± 0.25 - $76.65 \pm 0.15\%$ w/w. Results demonstrated that increase in concentration of polymer increased the entrapment of the drug. The drug entrapment efficiency was found to be good in all the formulations. The maximum drug entrapment was found in formulation F-5 (76.62 ± 0.15).

Table 3: Drug entrapment for different formulations

S. No.	Formulation	Drug Entrapment (% w/w) of Prepared Microsphere
1.	F1	63.25 ± 0.21
2.	F2	65.45 ± 0.25
3.	F3	68.85 ± 0.36
4.	F4	72.25 ± 0.21
5.	F5	76.62 ± 0.15

Figure 9: Drug entrapment for different formulation

Percentage Buoyancy and floating lag time of floating microsphere

The percentage buoyancies of formulations F1–F3 at the end of 10 h were found to be $72.25 \pm 0.32\%$, $69.95 \pm 0.42\%$ and $73.32 \pm 0.25\%$, and for the formulations F4–F6 at the end of 10 h were $73.25 \pm 0.42\%$, $79.92 \pm 0.36\%$, and $71.15 \pm 0.41\%$. The result indicates that with an increase in the concentration of polymers, Eudragit RL 100 and HPMC slight decrease the floating time (table 4). Formulations F5 of prepared microspheres were found to be the best compare to other formulation. The Floating Lag Time (Sec.) lag time of formulation F5 was also found less (52 ± 6), compare to other formulation.

Table 4: Percentage Buoyancy and floating lag time of floating microsphere

Formulation	Floating Lag Time (Sec.)	Percentage Buoyancy
F1	73 ± 4	72.25 ± 0.32
F2	69 ± 3	69.95 ± 0.42
F3	78 ± 5	73.32 ± 0.25
F4	76 ± 3	73.25 ± 0.42
F5	52 ± 6	79.92 ± 0.36

The maximum percentage yield, drug entrapment, percentage buoyancy and less floating lag time was found to be formulation F5 in floating microsphere. The optimized formulation of batche subjected to further studies.

Figure 10: Floating lag time and percentage buoyancy for different formulation

Particle size analysis

The mean size of the microspheres was determined by photo correlation spectroscopy (PCS) on a submicron particle size analyzer (Horiba Instruments) at a scattering angle of 90°. A sample (0.5mg) of the microspheres suspended in 5 ml of distilled water was used for the measurement. The results of measurement of mean particle size of optimized formulation F5 of floating microsphere was found to be 210.25 nm.

Figure 11: Particle size data of optimized microsphere formulation F5

Zeta Potential

The zeta potential of the drug-loaded microspheres was measured on a zeta sizer (Malvern Instruments) by determining the electrophoretic mobility in a micro electrophoresis flow cell. All the samples were measured in water at 25°C in triplicate. Results of zeta potential of optimized formulation F5 of floating microsphere was found - 38.58 mV.

Figure 12: Zeta potential data of floating microsphere F5

Shape and Surface Characterization of Microspheres by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Figure 13: Graph of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of optimized formulation F5

In vitro drug release study of Nizatidine loaded microsphere
Comparative release study of all formulation F1-F6

Table 5: Release Study data of formulation F1-F6

Time (Hrs)	% of Drug Release						
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	Marketed Formulation (Nizatidine 150mg Tablet)
0.5	37.85	34.45	31.15	26.65	25.56	22.25	36.65
1	49.98	45.58	35.65	39.98	33.32	31.14	63.32
2	63.32	60.23	43.32	45.58	42.25	40.56	95.56
4	78.85	70.23	68.85	63.32	58.85	50.14	99.12
6	86.65	76.65	71.14	75.65	69.98	63.32	-
8	98.12	93.32	89.98	83.32	78.85	75.65	-
10	99.45	99.45	99.85	98.85	89.98	82.23	-
12	99.65	99.95	99.96	99.85	99.74	89.98	-

Graph of release study of formulation F1-F6

Figure 14: Graph of release study of formulation F1-F6

Table 6: Release Kinetics of optimized formulation of microsphere F3

Time (h)	Square Root of Time(h) ^{1/2}	Log Time	Cumulative % DrugRelease	Log Cumulative % Drug Released	Cumulative % Drug Remaining	Log Cumulative % Drug Remaining
0.5	0.707	-0.301	25.56	1.408	74.44	1.872
1	1.000	0.000	33.32	1.523	66.68	1.824
2	1.414	0.301	42.25	1.626	57.75	1.762
4	2.000	0.602	58.85	1.770	41.15	1.614
6	2.449	0.778	69.98	1.845	30.02	1.477
8	2.828	0.903	78.85	1.897	21.15	1.325
10	3.162	1.000	89.98	1.954	10.02	1.001
12	3.464	1.079	99.74	1.999	0.26	-0.585

Zero order release kinetics of optimized formulations

Figure 15: Zero order release kinetics graph of optimized formulations

First order release kinetics of optimized formulations

Figure 16: First order release kinetics graph of optimized formulations

Higuchi release kinetics of optimized formulations

Figure 17: Higuchi release kinetics graph of optimized formulations

Korsmeyer peppas release kinetics of optimized formulations

Figure 18: Graph of Korsmeyer Peppas release kinetics of optimized formulations

Table 7: Comparative study of regression coefficient for selection of optimized Formulation F3

Release Kinetics	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer peppas
R^2	0.980	0.729	0.997	0.995

The In vitro drug release data of the optimized formulation was subjected to goodness of fit test by linear regression analysis according to zero order, first order kinetic equation, in order to determine the mechanism of drug release. When the regression coefficient values were compared, it was observed that an 'r' value of microsphere was

maximum Higuchi release i.e 0.997 hence indicating drug releases from formulations was found to follow Higuchi release kinetics for floating microsphere.

Stability studies of final formulation

According to ICH guidelines, 3 months accelerated stability study at $40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75\pm 5\%$ RH optimized formulations (F5) was carried out. It showed negligible change over time for parameters like appearance, drug content, dissolution and assay etc., No significant difference observed in the drug content between initial and formulations stored at $40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & $75\pm 5\%$ RH for 3 months.

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